

Type specimens of Acari (Arachnida) in the collections of the National Museum of Natural History, Sofia. I. Acariformes (Acaridida and Prostigmata)

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Abstract: The present list contains data on type material of 109 mite species (Acaridida and Prostigmata) from Bulgaria (species, described by I. Vassilev, M. Kolebinova, P. Beron) and many foreign countries: Greece, Suriname, the Netherlands, New Guinea, Cuba, Mexico, Chile, USA, Canada, Madagascar, Gaboon, Liberia, Nigeria, Uganda, Mozambique, Tanzania, Zambia, Morocco, Tunisia, Malaysia, Burma, Thailand, China, and the Philippines (species, described by M. Kolebinova, P. Beron, F. Lukoschus, A. Fain, C. Welbourn, F. Dusbábek, K. Samšinák, K. R. Orwig, W. Ateyo and other authors). The type material housed in the National Museum of Natural History, Sofia includes species from the families Acaridae, Glycyphagidae, Canestriniidae, Proctophyllodidae, Trouessartiidae, Syringobiidae, Dermationidae, Ereyntidae, Cytoditidae, Myocoptidae, Chirodiscidae, Gastronyssidae, Myobiidae, Ophioptidae, Demodicidae, Smarididae, Erythraeidae, Neotrombidiidae, Eutrombidiidae, Trombiculidae, Leeuwenhoekiiidae, Walchiidae, and Vatacaridae. All Bulgarian and foreign acarologists are kindly invited to submit type specimens under their care in the collections of the National Museum of Natural History in Sofia. This material will be properly housed and well used.

Keywords: Acari, Astigmata, museum, Prostigmata, Sofia, type specimens

Introduction

The descriptions of new taxa of Acari by Bulgarian acarologists start rather late. First, Drenski described the tick *Argas bureshi* Drenski, 1957. The type specimens of this species are currently missing and the efforts to be found after the death of Drenski in 1963 have not been successful. New feather mites from Bulgaria were described by Iv. Vassilev (1958–1965, partly in co-operation with M. Kolebinova, W. Ateyo and J. Gaud). Petar Beron and M. Kolebinova started describing mites simultaneously in 1965 and became the first Bulgarians describing Acari from other countries. Most of the type specimens of Vassilev, Kolebinova and Beron are now preserved in the National Museum of Natural History in Sofia (NMNHS). More mites, almost entirely from Bulgaria, have been described by A. Petrova (water mites), E. Angelkova (Acaridida),

M. Jeleva (Oribatida), P. Natchev (Eryophyoidea), M. Koymdjieva (Mesostigmata), and D. Dobrev (Scutacaridae). Efforts are made to house their type specimens (now in other zoological institutions) also in the NMNHS. At the same time, many types (usually paratypes) of Acari, described by foreign specialists (F. Dusbábek, K. Samšinák, F. Lukoschus, W. Ateyo, C. Welbourn, P. H. Vercammen-Grandjean), have been donated to their Bulgarian colleagues and are now in the collections of the NMNHS. They are marked with different numbers and other marking of their initial institutions. This marking is mentioned with the description of the label data.

Remaining almost the only acarologist in Bulgaria still describing mites, I tried to organise and to arrange in the collections of the NMNHS all type specimens of Acari, available in Bulgaria, of all groups. I was facilitated by the generous donation of the many

types in possession of my retired colleague Mrs Maria Kolebinova. In the present list are included the types of 109 species of Acari (incl 52 holotypes) of the suborders Acaridida and Prostigmata from Bulgaria (described by I. Vassilev, M. Kolebinova, P. Beron, and F. Dusbábek), as well as from many foreign countries (Greece, France, Romania, the Czech Republic, the Netherlands, Trinidad, Suriname, Bolivia, Chile, Peru, Mexico, Cuba, the USA, Canada, Madagascar, Nigeria, Gaboon, Kenya, Uganda, Mozambique, Somalia, Tanzania, Liberia, Tunisia, Morocco, the Philippines, Nepal, Malaysia, Indonesia, Thailand, Burma, China, and New Guinea), described by M. Kolebinova, P. Beron, F. Lukoschus, A. Fain, C. Welbourn, K. R. Orwig, W. Atyeo, Z. Feider, K. Samšinak, and other authors. The type specimens of Acari deposited in the NMNHS represent species belonging to the families Acaridae, Glycyphagidae, Canestriniidae, Proctophylodidae, Trouessartiidae, Syringobiidae, Dermationidae, Ereynetidae, Cytoditidae, Myocoptidae, Chirodiscidae, Gastronyssidae, Myobiidae, Ophioptidae, Demodicidae, Smarididae, Erythraeidae, Neotrombidiidae, Eutrombidiidae, Trombiculidae, Walchiidae, Leeuwenhoekiiidae, and Vatacaridae.

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List of type specimens

Acari

Acariformes

Sarcoptiformes

Astigmata (Acaridida)

Acaridae

- *Sancassania phyllognathi* Samšinak – (Samšinak, 1970: 404 [2 slides]). Label data: “Paratype[s], ♂♀, leg. Hurpin” [data from the description].
- *Sancassania berteaeursae* Samšinak – (Samšinak, 1970: 407 [2 slides]). Label data: “Paratype[s], ♂♀, Rum[ania], Donau Delta Gebiet, 17.7.1969”.

Glycyphagidae

- *Orycteroxenus canadensis* Fain, Kok, Lukoschus & Clulow – (Fain et al., 1971: 16). Label data: “Paratype, hypopus, *Condylura cristata* [Soricomorpha, Talpidae], Sudbury [Canada], 17.7.1969, Lukoschus leg.”.

Canestriniidae

- *Canestrinia samsinaki* Beron – (Beron, 1975c: 83 [7 slides]). Label data: “Holotype ♂, ex *Gnaptor* sp. [Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae], Sozopol, Bulgaria, 25.6.1968, P. Beron leg.”. On the same slide are mounted also 1 ♀, 2 ♂. On the other six slides are mounted 2 ♂♂, 17 ♀♀ paratypes, incl. allotype, 1 larva.

Cytoditidae

- *Cytodites faini* Beron – (Beron, 1975b: 185 [5 slides]). Label data: 1. “Holotype ♀, ex *Lanius collurio* [Laniidae], Pazardjik, Bulgaria, 10.6.1968, P. Beron leg.”. 2–5. “Paratype[s], ex *Lanius collurio*, Pazardjik, Bulgaria, 10.6.1968, P. Beron leg.”.

Myocoptidae

- *Trichoecius apodemi* Fain, Munting & Lukoschus – (Fain et al., 1969: 391). Label data: “Paratype ♀, ex *Apodemus sylvaticus* [Muridae], NL[Nederlands] – Hatert, 14.11.1966, Lukoschus leg.”.
- *Gliricoptes eliomys* Kok, Lukoschus & Fain – (Kok et al., 1971: 50). Label data: “Paratype ♀, ex *Eliomys quercinus* [Rodentia, Myoxidae], Gafsa, Tunis, 1914, Nat. Mus. Wien, Lukoschus leg.”.

Chirodiscidae

- *Alabidocarpus balcanicus* Beron – (Beron, 1965: 255). Note: Currently synonymised by Fain (1971) with *Alabidocarpus megalonyx megalonyx* (Trouessart, 1895). Label data: “Holotypus ♀, ex *Rhin[olophus] ferrumequinum* [Chiroptera, Rhinolophidae], Batulija, Bulgarie, mine, 6.9.1964, P. Beron leg.”.
- *Lutrilichus nivalis* Beron – (Beron, 1973: 537). Label data: “Holotypus, ♀, Châlet Vichren, alt. 2050 m, Pirin, Bulgarie du Sud-Ouest, 28.VIII.1969, A. Lateva leg., ex *Mustela nivalis* L. (Mustelidae)”.
- *Lawrenceocarpus micropilus* Dusbábek & Cruz – (Dusbábek & Cruz, 1966: 12). Label data: “Paratype, ♀, ex *Chilonycteris fuliginosa torrei* [Chi-

roptera], Cueva del Indio, Tapaste, La Habana, 10.1.1966, Dusbábek & de la Cruz leg.”.

Proctophyllodidae

- *Proctophyllodes emberizae* Atyeo & Vassilev – (Atyeo & Vassilev, 1964: 273). Label data: 1 slide – “Holotype ♂, Allotype ♀, [ex] *Emberiza melanocephala* [Emberizidae], [II max. (quart.) v. Ognyanovo, Distr. Pazardjik] (in Bulgarian), 11.VII.1960, No 889/20a”.
- *Proctophyllodes tenericaulus* Atyeo & Vassilev – (Atyeo & Vassilev, 1964: 275). Label data: “Holotype ♂, Allotype ♀, [on one slide] *Turdus viscivorus* [Turdidae], “I max. [quart.] G. Deltchev 20.X.1960 Iv. Vassilev leg.” (in Bulgarian), No 2553 (Notebook No 96b, in Bulgarian).
- *Tanyphyllodes scelorhilaie* Atyeo – (Atyeo, 1966a: 473). Label data: “Paratype[s], ex *Scelorhilus r. rubecula* (Rhinocryptidae), Purn, Mallico Prov., Chile, 7 Oct. 1960, J. K. Greer, NU 9580 (MichSU 3624), Univ. Nebraska Mus.”.
- *Nycteridocaulus tyranni* Atyeo – (Atyeo, 1966b: 489 [2 slides]). 1. Label data: “Paratype ♂, ex *Contopus pertinax* [Greater Peewee], [Tyrannidae], Pendencia, San Luis Potosi, Mexico, 28. 5. 1954, L. Guerrero leg.; Univ. Nebraska Mus., NU 2018”. 2. Label data: “Paratype ♂, ex *Contopus pertinax* (Greater Peewee), Pendencia, San Luis Potosi, Mexico, 28. 5. 1954, L. Guerrero leg.; Univ. Nebraska Mus., NU 2018”.
- *Nycteridocaulus bilobatus* Atyeo – (Atyeo, 1966b: 483). Label data: “Paratype[s], ♀, ♂, ex *Sayornis n. nigricans* [Tyrannidae], Rio Ramos, 20 km, NW Montemorelos N.L., Mexico, 8.6. 1942, W.B. Davis leg., NU 1555, Univ. Nebraska Mus.”.

Syringobiidae

- *Ascouracarus vassilevi* [Gaud & Kolebinova] – (Gaud & Kolebinova, 1973: 349 [3 slides]). 1. Label: “Holotype ♂, Sofia, *Caprimulgus europaeus* [Caprimulgidae], 12.X.1958 Leg. I. Vassilev; No 682a/262. 2. Label: “Allotype ♀, Sofia, *Caprimulgus europaeus* 12.X.1958 Leg. I. Vassilev; No 682/262. 3. Label: “Paratype ♀, Sofia, *Caprimulgus europaeus* 12.X.1958 Leg. I. Vassilev; No 682/262.”.

Dermationidae

- *Dermation gallinulae* Lukoschus, Fain & Driessen – (Lukoschus et al., 1969: 55). Label data:

“Paratype, ♀, ex *Gallinula chloropus* [Rallidae], Nijmegen [the Netherlands], 13.1.1967”.

- *Passeroptes [Rivoltasia] gaudi* (Vassilev & Kolebinova) – (Vassilev & Kolebinova, 1965: 161). Label data: “H[olotype], ♀, Ex *Sturnus vulgaris* [Sturnidae], v. Tchelopechene near Sofia, 27.IX.1962, Iv. Vassilev leg. & det., 445(81)” (in Bulgarian).

Trouessartiidae

- *Neocalcealges segregatus* Orwig – (Orwig, 1968: 148). Label data: “Paratype [s], ♀, ♂, ex *Stachyris nigriceps davisoni* [Timaliidae], Mt. Brinchang, Pahang, Malaya, USA Med. Res. Unit, 23.11.1961, ser No MOO444, NV 6563”.
- *Neocalcealges undulatus* Orwig – (Orwig, 1968: 151 [2 slides]). 1. Label data: “Paratype ♀, ex *Heterophasia picaoides*, Long – tailed Sibia [Timaliidae], Mt. Brinchang, Pahang, Malaya, USA Med. Res. Unit, K.L. [1961], Ser.No M – 00483, BA 14836, NU 6602”. 2. Label data: “Paratype ♂, the other data the same”.
- *Bicentralges orientalis* Orwig – (Orwig, 1966: 39 [2 slides]). 1. Label data: “Paratype ♂, ex *Cymbirhynchus macrorhynchus* (Eurylaimidae), 7.12.1961, Rantau, Panjang, Selangor, Malaya, USA Med.Res.Unit K.L., Ser.No M – 00598, NU – 6700”. 2. Label data: “Paratype ♀, same data”.
- *Bicentralges psarisomi* Orwig – (Orwig, 1966: 42 [2 slides]). 1. Label data: “Paratype ♂, ex *Psarisomus dalhousiae* (Eurylaimidae), ? Pang Wua Yao, E. Burma, 27.1. 1933, H.M. Smith leg., USNM 332849; NU 9304”. 2. Label data: “Paratype ♀, the other data are the same”.
- *Bicentralges vebulla* Orwig – (Orwig, 1966: 50 [2 slides]). 1. Label data: “Paratype ♂, ex *Stachyris nigricollis* (Timaliidae), 16.1.1963, Meru, Malaya, USA Med.Res.Unit K.L., Ser. No M – 02194, NU – 7769”. 2. Label data: “Paratype ♀, the other data are the same”.
- *Bicentralges caulatus* Orwig – (Orwig, 1966: 51 [2 slides]). 1. Label data: “Paratype ♂, ex *Stachyris nigriceps* (Timaliidae), Doi Pui, Chieng Mai, Thailand, USA Med.Res.Unit, 11.2.1965, Ser.No 5E1065; NU 20766”. 2. Label data: “Paratype ♀, the other data are the same”.
- *Bicentralges miscellus* Orwig – (Orwig, 1966: 30 [2 slides]). 1. Label data: “Paratype ♂, ex *Cymbirhynchus macrorhynchus* (Eurylaimidae), 31.1.1963, Gombak, Malaya, USA Med. Res.

Unit, K.L., Ser.No M – 02264; NU – 7824”. 2. Label data: “Paratype ♀, the other data are the same”.

- *Bicentralges longivasatus* Orwig – (Orwig, 1966: 46 [2 slides]). 1. Label data: “Paratype ♂, ex *Malacopteron cinereum* (Timaliidae), Gombak, Malaya, USA, Med. Res. Unit, 29.1.1963, Ser.No M – 02259; NU 7819”. 2. Label data: “Paratype ♀, the other data are the same”.
- *Arthrogynalges biovoidatus* Orwig – (Orwig, 1968: 60 [2 slides]). 1. Label data: “Paratype ♂, *Philepitta jala* (Philepittidae), Madagascar, NU 9480 (USNM 145253)”. 2. Label data: “Paratype ♀, the other data are the same”.
- *Calcealges novimundus* Orwig – (Orwig, 1966: 128 [2 slides]). 1. Label data: “Paratype ♀, ex *Thamnophilus doliatus* (Formicariidae), Caroni River, La Paille Village, Trinidad, West Indies, 21.12.1960, T.H.G. Aitken, NU 8484”. 2. Label data: “Paratype ♂, ex *Thamnophilus doliatus* (Formicariidae), Ravine Sable Trace, Vega de Oropouche, Trinidad, West Indies, 13.9.1960, NU 458”.

Sarcoptidae

- *Notoedes (Bakeracarus) lasionycteris minimus* Dusbábek – (Dusbábek, 1970: 272). Label data: “Paratype ♀, ex *Molossus tropidorhynchus*, Coca Sala, Marianao, Havana, Cuba, 10.4.1965, F. Dusbábek”.
- *Notoedes (Bakeracarus) lasionycteris intermedius* Dusbábek – (Dusbábek, 1970: 274). Label data: “Paratype ♀, ex *Tadarida minuta*, Cueva Yaguajay, Cuba, 10.6.1965, F. Dusbábek leg.”.

Trombidiformes

Prostigmata

Ereynetidae

- *Speleochir carolliae* Fain & Lukoschus – (Fain & Lukoschus, 1971: 246). Label data: “Paratype, ♀, ex *Carollia perspicillata* [Phyllostomatidae], Lelydorp, Suriname, 15.12.1969, Lukoschus leg.”.
- *Neospeleognathopsis (Speleomyotis) molossus* Fain & Lukoschus – (Fain & Lukoschus, 1971: 285). Label data: “Paratype, ♀, ex *Molossus*

molossus, Paramaribo [Suriname], 1.1.1970, Lukoschus leg. 208”.

- *Hipposideroptes saccopteryx* Fain & Lukoschus – (Fain & Lukoschus, 1971: 289). Label data: “Paratype, ex *Saccopteryx bilineata* [Chiroptera], Lelydorp, Suriname, 26. 2. 1970, Lukoschus leg., 484”.

Myobiidae

- *Protomyobia onoi* Jameson & Dusbábek – (Jameson & Dusbábek, 1971: 33 [2 slides]). Label data: 1. “Paratype ♂, ex *Sorex araneus*, Potok z Černeho dolu, 27.9.1964, exp. ČSAV, Dusbábek Jameson det.”. 2. “Paratype ♀, ex *Sorex araneus*, Veltrusy, 3.5.1967, Černý, det. Dusbábek, Jameson”.
- *Pteracarus aculeus* Dusbábek & Lukoschus – (Dusbábek & Lukoschus, in Dusbábek, 1973: 246). Label data: “Paratype ♀ 504, ex *Eptesicus melanopterus* [Vespertilionidae], Meerzorg, [Suriname], 3.3.1970, Lukoschus leg.”.
- *Neomyobia myoti* Dusbábek – (Dusbábek, 1963: 237 [2 slides]). Now *Acanthophthirius myoti*. Label data: 1. “Paratype ♀, 1132, ex *Myotis myotis* [Vespertilionidae], Dobříš [Czech Rep.], 26.9.1959, F. Dusbábek leg.”. 2. “Paratype ♂, ex *Myotis myotis*, Dobříš [Czech Rep.], 21.9.1959, F. Dusbábek leg.”.
- *Myobia micromydis* Lukoschus & Driessen – (Lukoschus & Driessen, 1970: 119). Slide 1: Label data: “Paratype, ♀, ex *Micromys minutus* Pall., Nijmegen, Nederland, 30.9.1968”. Slide 2: Label data: “Paratype, 2 ♂♂, ex *Micromys minutus* Pall., Nijmegen, Nederland, 30.9.1968”.
- *Eadiea multisetosa* Lukoschus & Driessen – (Lukoschus & Driessen, 1969: 383). Now: *Crocidurobia (Suncomyobia) multisetosa* (Lukoschus & Driessen). Label data: “Paratype ♂, ex *Crocidura russula* [Soricidae], Helmond, 16.4.1968, H. Strybosch leg.”.
- *Amorphacarus parvisetosus* Lukoschus & Driessen – (Lukoschus & Driessen, 1971: 163). Label data: “Paratype ♂, ♀, *Neomys fodiens* [Soricidae], Hatert [Nederland], 15.9.1968; Paratype ♀, same data”.
- *Archemyobia philander* Lukoschus, Dusbábek & Jameson – (Lukoschus et al., 1972). Label data: “Paratype, ♀, ex *Philander opossum*, Lelydorp, Surinam, 56, 17-7-71, Lukoschus & Kok leg.”.
- *Jamesonia danieli* (Dusbábek) – (Dusbábek, 1967: 248). Now: *Eudusbabekia (Eudusbabekia)*

- danieli* (Dusbábek, 1967). Label data: “Paratype ♀, ex *Phyllonycteris poeyi* [Chiroptera, Phyllostomatidae], Cueva del Mudo, La Habana, [Cuba], 4.2.1966, F. Dusbábek & J. de la Cruz leg.”.
- *Jamesonia viguerasi* Dusbábek – (Dusbábek, 1967: 257). Now: *Eudusbabekia (Eudusbabekia) viguerasi* (Dusbábek). Label data: “Paratype ♀, ex *Artibeus jamaicensis parvipes* [Chiroptera, Phyllostomatidae], Cueva Bonila, Camaguey, Cuba, 29.10.1965”.
- *Ugandobia (Expletobia) procera* Dusbábek & Lukoschus – (Dusbábek & Lukoschus, 1971: 341). Label data: “Paratype ♀, ex *Saccopteryx bilineata* [Chiroptera, Phyllostomatidae], Lelydorp [Suriname], 20. 2. 1970, Lukoschus leg.”.
- Ophioptidae**
- *Ophioptes beshkovi* Beron – (Beron, 1974: 691). Label data: “Holotype ♀, ex *Coluber najadum dahli* [Serpentes: Colubridae], v. Frolosh, Bulg., 11.6.1968, P. Beron leg.”.
- Demodicidae**
- *Demodex carolliae* Desch, Lebel, Nutting & Lukoschus – (Desch et al., 1971: 303). Label data: “Paratypes, ex *Carollia perspicillata* [Chiroptera, Phyllostomatidae], Suriname, Lelydorp, 11.12.1969, Lukoschus leg.”.
- Smarididae**
- *Trichosmaris papuana* Beron – (Beron, 2002: 76). Label data: “Holotype ♂, [Papua] New Guinea, Western Province, top of Mt. Fugilil, 3100 m, 30.9.1975, P. Beron leg.”.
- Erythraeidae**
- Erythraeinae**
- *Erythraeus bulgaromontanus* Beron – (Beron, 1982: 50). Label data: “Holotype larva, Rila, Mussala, 2925 m, 8.08.1971, P. Beron leg.”.
- *Erythraeus rilensis* Beron – (Beron, 1982: 55). Label data: “Holotype larva, Rila, Grančar, 2250 m, 16.08.1973, P. Beron leg.”.
- *Erythraeus kresnensis* Beron – (Beron, 1982: 47). Label data: “Bulgaria SW, Kresnensko hantche, under stone, 25.04.1971, 1 larva (Holotype)”.
- *Erythraeus (Helladerythraeus) pachytibialis* Beron – (Beron, 1988: 3 [4 slides]). Note: currently *Helladerythraeus pachytibialis* (Beron). Label data: 1 – “Holotype, Rhodes, Lindos, 0-100 m, 30.4.1984, P. Beron leg.”. 2,3,4 – “Paratype[s], “[Greece], I. Kithnos, v. Dryopis, 16.5.1984, P. Beron leg.”.
- *Curteria graeca* Beron – (Beron, 1988: 10). Label data: 13 slides with paratypes (Greece, I. Kithnos, v. Dryopis, 16.5.1984 – 1 slide; Rhodes, Laerma Village, 1.5.1984 – 1 slide; Rhodes, v. Lardos, 1.5.1984 – 1 slide; Rhodes, Lindos, 0-100 m, 30.4.1984 – 9 slides; Crete, Psiloritis, 700-900 m, 13.5.1984 – 1 slide).
- *Paraphanolophus halffteri* Beron – (Beron, 1996: 25). Label data: “Holotype larva, Mexico, Tabasco, Teapa, 23.1.1982, P. Beron leg.”.
- Leptinae**
- *Leptus echinopus* Beron – (Beron, 1975: 60). Label data for 4 slides: “Holotype (larva), Bulgaria, Longosa, ex *Tomocerus* sp. (Collembola), 30.07.1968, P. Beron leg.”. Three paratypes (larvae) on three slides with the same data.
- *Leptus treati* Welbourn – (Welbourn, in Welbourn & Jennings, 1991: 569). Label data: “AL – 2959 USA, Maine Piscataquis Co. Baxter State Park 1 km SSE Nesowadnehunk Meadow 16-VII-1984 W.C. Welbourn & D.T. Jennings colls.”.
- *Leptus josifovi* Beron – (Beron, 1975: 49). Label data: “Holotypus (larva), Bulg., Ropotamo, ex *Acmeodera* sp. (Coleoptera: Buprestidae), on the head, 26.07. 1968, P. Beron leg.”.
- *Leptus orthopterarum* Beron – (Beron, 1975: 52). Label data: [in Bulgarian], v. Primorsko, Burgas District, ex *Bucephaloptera bucephala* [Orthoptera], 26. 7. 1968, P. Beron leg., Holotype, 1 l[arva] re-mounted, P. Beron det. (NMNHS).
- *Leptus slivovi* Beron – (Beron, 1975: 54). Label data: “1 larva, Holotype, Bulg., Distr. Burgas, Ropotamo, ex *Laelia coenosa* (Lepidoptera), 19.07.1973, Host collected by Al. Slivov”.
- *Leptus meloidarum* Beron – (Beron, 1975: 56). Label data: “Holotypus (larva), Bulg., near Vraca, ex Meloidae (Coleoptera), 24.09.1068, P. Beron leg.” (NMNHS).
- *Leptus southcotti* Beron – (Beron, 1975: 47). Label data: “Holotype (larva), ex Collembola, v. Ropot, Bulgarie, 5.7.1969, P. Beron leg.”.
- Callidosomatinae**
- *Charletonia bucephalia* Beron – (Beron, 1975: 73). Label data: “Holotypus, larva, re-mounted!

v. Primorsko, Distr. Burgas, Bulgaria, ex *Bucephaloptera bucephala* (Orthoptera), 25.7.1968, P. Beron leg.”.

- *Caeculisoma haussa* Beron – (Beron, 2000: 66). Label data: “Holotype 1 ♀ ad., Maiduguri, Northern Nigeria, 20.09.1976”.
- *Cecidopus nigeriae* Beron – (Beron, 2000: 70). Label data: “Holotype ♂, Nigeria, Plateau State, Wase Rock Game Reserve, under stone, 01.06.1978.”.

Myrmicotrombiinae

- *Myrmicotrombium* (*Graecotrombium*) *mirum* Beron – (Beron, 1990: 69). Label data: “Holotype, ♂, Greece, Attika, v. Keratea, 17.5.1984, P. Beron leg.; [seen by R. Southcott and marked by him with No ACA 2139].”.

Neotrombidiidae

- *Neotrombidium cubanum* Beron – (Beron, 1995: 13). Label data: “Holotype larva, ex Cerambycidae [Coleoptera], sub el[ytrae], Cuba, Prov. Santiago de Cuba, Punta Agujas, 4.3.1982, P. Beron leg.”. Paratypes, the same data.

Eutrombidiidae

- *Eutrombidium lockleii* [sic!; should be “*lockleyi*”] Welbourn & Young – (Welbourn & Young, 1988: 374). Label data: “USA, Mississippi, Sunflower Co., 3.3 km SSW Indianola ex *Ceraticelus emertoni* (Araneae, Linyphiidae) 19-VII-1984 T.C. Lockley coll. original no. S – 38 OSUAL – 3298”.

Trombiculidae

- *Walchiella oudemansi katangladensis* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1984b: 40 [11 slides]). Label data: “Paratype larva, ex *Nannosciurus surrutilus* [Scuridae], Mt. Katanglad, Mindanao, Philippines, Bregulla, 10. 1965, SMF 29536” – the same on all slides.
- *Walchiella philippinensis* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1984b: 42). Label data: “Paratype larva, ex *Rattus insignis* [Muridae], Mt. Katanglad, Mindanao, Philippines, Bregulla, 10. 1965, SMF 30937/W/2; L = 01065/W/2”.
- *Leptotrombidium* (*Ericotrombidium*) *rheinwaldi* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1979b: 487 [6 slides]). Label data: “Paratype[s] larvae, ex *Elephantulus rozeti* [Macroscelididae], Parondant, Maroko,

- 7.3.7.3.1975, O. Rheinwald leg.; 731975/24” – same data on all slides.
- *Gerbillicula deserta* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1984a: 73 [8 slides]). 1. Label data: “Paratype larva, Gabes, Tunesien, Spatz 1898, SMF 9660 / 6/4. 2–8. Label data: “same data, SMF 9660/8/11; 9660/8/12; 9660/8/13; 9660/8/14; 9660/8/15; 9660/8/16; 9660/8/17; 9660/8/19”.
- *Afrotrombicula* (*Afrotrombicula*) *gabonica* Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean – (Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean, 1981: 415 [4 slides]). 1. Label data: “Paratype larva, ex *Atherurus africanus* [Hystricidae], Makokou, Gabon, 3.1.1964, van Bree leg., Amsterdam 7507/A 7,8; L = 3164/A/7,8”. 2. Label data: same data, 7507/A/13. 3. Label data: same data, 7507/A/5. 4. Label data: same data, 7507/A/2.
- *Leptotrombidium* (*Leptotrombidium*) *subobscurum* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1980: 70). Label data: “Paratype larva, ex *Rattus insignis* [Muridae], Mt. Katanglad, Mindanao, 10.1965, Bregulla, SMF 30937; L = 01065/S/1”.
- *Neotrombicula* (*Neotrombicula*) *anthiana* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1969: 5 [2 slides]). 1. Label data: “Holotype larva, ex *Anthus trivialis* [Motacillidae], Belogradchik, Bulgaria, 19.9.1963, Kolebinova leg., 10/75 – 236” (NM-NHS). 2. Label data: “Paratype larva, ex *Anthus trivialis* [Motacillidae], Belogradchik, Bulgaria, 19.9.1963, Kolebinova leg., 1/ 75a – 236”.
- *Neotrombicula* (*H[offmannina]*) *danieli* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1974a: 971). Now *Xinjiangsha danieli* (Kolebinova). Label data: “Holotype larva, ex *Sylvaemus* [*Apodemus*] *sylvaticus* [Muridae], Blagoevgrad, Bulgaria, 17.3.1967, Kolebinova leg., 27/1”.
- *Neotrombicula* (*H[offmannina]*) *monticola* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1974a: 971 [2 slides]). Now *Xinjiangsha* (= *Aboriginesia* [Kudryashova, 1993] *monticola* (Kolebinova). 1. Label data: “Holotype larva, ex *Clethrionomys* [*Myodes*] *glareolus*, [Cricetidae], Vihren [Pirin], Bulgaria, 28.8.1969, Kolebinova leg., 26/162”. 2. Label data: “Paratype larva, same data, 162”.
- *Neotrombicula* (*Hoffmannina*) *galla* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1970: 98). Label data: “Holotype larva, ex *Apodemus sylvaticus* [Muridae], Moulis, Ariège, France, 13.10.1967, P. Beron leg., 13/12”.
- *Neotrombicula* (*Hoffmannina*) *talpae* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1977: 62 [10 slides]). Currently

- Xinjiangsha* (= *Aboriginesia* Kudryashova, 1993) *talpae* (Kolebinova). 1. Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Talpa europaea* [Talpidae], Maslen nos, reserv. Ropotamo, Bulgarie, 21.4.1973, M. Kolebinova leg., 29/24". 2–10. Label data: "Paratype[s] larvae, ex *Talpa europaea* [Talpidae], Maslen nos, reserv. Ropotamo, Bulgarie, 21.4.1973, M. Kolebinova leg., 1/24; 2/24; 3/24; 4/24; 5/24; 6/24; 7/24; 8/24; 9/24".
- *Neotrombicula* (*Hoffmannina*) *vercammengrandjeani* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1971: 1397 [4 slides]). Now *Xinjiangsha* (= *Aboriginesia* Kudryashova, 1993) *vercammengrandjeani*. 1. Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Clethrionomys* [= *Myodes*] *glareolus* [Cricetidae], Witinja, Bulgarie, 7.10.1967, M. Kolebinova leg., 18/237". 2. Label data: "Paratype larva, ex *Myodes* [= *Clethrionomys glareolus*], Witinja, Bulgarie, 7.10.1967, M. Kolebinova leg.; on the same slide also *N. zachvatkini* and *N. inopinata*". 3–4. Label data: "Paratype[s] larvae, ex *Clethrionomys* [= *Myodes*] *glareolus* [Cricetidae], Witinja, Bulgarie, 7.10.1967, M. Kolebinova leg., 1/237; 2/237".
 - *Neotrombicula* (*Neotrombicula*) *serbovae* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1972: 673). Now *Eutonella serbovae* (Kolebinova). Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Apodemus flavicollis* [Muridae], Vrana [nr. Sofia, Bulgaria, 16.10.1968, S. Serbova leg., 23/206".
 - *Neotrombicula* (*Neotrombicula*) *rhinolophi* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1968: 113). Currently *Neotrombicula* (*Arctrombicula*) *rhinolophi* Kolebinova. Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Rhinolophus hipposideros* [Chiroptera, Rhinolophidae], Dolna Beshovica, g[rotte] Dupna mogila, Bulgaria, 7.2.1964, P. Beron leg., 6/9".
 - *Neotrombicula* (*Neotrombicula*) *sciuricola* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1969: 6). Now *Eutonella sciuricola* (Kolebinova). Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Sciurus vulgaris* [Sciuridae], Kalotino, Tcheparlanski monaster, Bulgaria, 24.10.1965, M. Kolebinova leg., 8/324 – 278".
 - *Neotrombicula* (*Neotrombicula*) *corvi* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1971a: 788). Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Corvus cornix* [Corvidae], Godetch, Bulgarie, 23.10.1965, Kolebinova leg., 22/322/974".
 - *Neotrombicula* (*Neotrombicula*) *creta* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1971d: 91). Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Rhinolophus hipposideros* [Chiroptera, Rhinolophidae], Grotte Crionerida, Crete, 15.1.1968, P. Beron leg., 16/24".
 - *Neotrombicula* (*Neotrombicula*) *boroveza* Vercammen-Grandjean, Kolebinova, Göksu & Kepka – (Vercammen-Grandjean et al., 1971: 1401). Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Sorex minutus* [Soricidae], Borovez, [Rila], Bulgarie, 9.10.1969, M. Kolebinova leg., 20/227".
 - *Neotrombicula* (*Neotrombicula*) *vandeli* Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean – (Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean, 1970: 174). Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Rhinolophus euryale* [Rhinolophidae], Grotte d'Oxybar, Pyrenées, France, 20.10.1967, P. Beron leg., 11/34".
 - *Neotrombicula* (*Neotrombicula*) *kepkaei* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1971a: 785). Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Apodemus sylvaticus* [Muridae], Gurkovo, Stara planina, [Bulgaria], 8.10.1968, M. Kolebinova leg., 21/583".
 - *Neotrombicula* (*Neotrombicula*) *balcanica* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1973: 695 [6 slides]). 1. Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Apodemus sylvaticus* [Muridae], Shipka to Stoletov, Bulgarie, 27.4.1967, M. Kolebinova leg., 24/950/225". 2–6. Label data: "Paratype [s], larvae, ex *Apodemus sylvaticus* [Muridae], Kasanlak, Bulgarie, 27. 4. 1967, M. Kolebinova leg., 1-5/950/225".
 - *Neotrombicula* (*Neotrombiculoides*) *elegantissima* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1981: 293). Label data: "Paratype larva, ex *Elephantulus rufescens* [Macroscelididae], Tanzania, Burungi, 11.9.1935, Kohl – Larsen [leg.], SMF 11798/N/4; L= 11955/N/4" (NMNHS).
 - *Neotrombicula* (*Tauffliebicula*) *liberia* Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean – (Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean, 1978: 106 [8 slides]). Label data: "Paratype[s], larvae, ex *Lophuromys sikapusi* [Muridae] Njeble [near Bongtown] Liberia, 16.10. 1970, Voelker leg., Hamburg T 882; L = 161070/N/2; /3; /4; /7; /11; /14; /16; /18".
 - *Miyatrombicula* (*Miyacarus*) *tokyoensis balcanica* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1969: 7). Currently *Miyatrombicula* (*Miyacarus*) *balcanica* Kolebinova. Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Sciurus vulgaris* [Sciuridae], Teteven, Bulgaria, 25.10.1966, M. Kolebinova leg., 9/701 – 92".
 - *Euschoengastia* (*Euschoengastia*) *europaea* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1971b: 915 [2 slides]). 1. Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Apodemus flavicollis* [Muridae], H[ut] Buzludja, Stara

- planina, Bulgarie, 25.9.1967, M. Kolebinova leg, 19/108/482". 2. Label data: "Paratype larva, ex *Apodemus flavicollis* [Muridae], H[ut] Buzludja, Stara planina, Bulgarie, 25.9.1967, M. Kolebinova leg, 108/482".
- *Schoengastiella (Dureniella) ocellata* Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean – (Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean, 1978: 113). Label data: "Paratype larva, ex *Lophuromys sikapusi* [Muridae], Njeble, Liberia, 16.10. 1970, Voelker leg., Hamburg T 882; L = 161070/0/2".
 - *Schoengastiella (Dureniella) subcoeca* Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean – (Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean, 1978: 115 [2 slides]). Label data: "Paratype larva, ex *Lophuromys sikapusi* [Muridae], Njeble, Liberia, 16.10. 1970, Voelker leg., Hamburg T 882; L = 161070/S/2; 161070/S/5".
 - *Schoengastia (Schoengastia) erinacei* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1984c: 110 [3 slides]). Label data: "Paratype larva, ex *Atelerix albiventris* [Erinaceidae], Mitteldamara [Namibia], 15.10. 1911, SMF 5825/S/10; L = 151011/S/10;- 5825/S/9; L = 151011/S/9;-5825/S/6; L = 5825/S/10; L = 151011/S/6".
 - *Microtrombicula (Microtrombicula) kikuyuensis* Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean – (Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean, 1980a: 65 [5 slides]). Label data: "Paratype[s], larvae, ex *Crocidura occidentalis* [Soricidae], Kikuyu, Kenya, 28.11.1902, NHM Wien, Lukoschus leg.; L = 281102/3; /4,5; /6; /7; /8".
 - *Microtrombicula (Crypticula) balcanica* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1982: 81). Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Rhinolophus hipposideros* [Rhinolophidae, on wing membrana, label in Bulgarian], [Cave] Dinevata peshtera, Ginci, [Bulgaria], 30.10.1967, No 30/37".
 - *Riedlinia (Riedlinia) europaea* Kolebinova & Beron – (Kolebinova & Beron, 1965: 71). Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Rhinolophus hipposideros* [Rhinolophidae], Cave Metcha dupka, v. Stradalovo, Distr. Kyustendil [label in Bulgarian], 27.2.1969, P. Beron leg., 1431/66".
 - *Riedlinia (Trombigastia) petarberoni* Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean – (Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean, 1970: 177). Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Rhinolophus euryale* [Rhinolophidae], Grotte Pietralbello, Corse, France, 24.11.1967, 12/33".
 - *Herpetacarus (Lukoschuskaaia) makokoui* Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean – (Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean, 1980b: 255). Label data: "Paratype larva, ex *Atherurus africanus* [Hystricidae], Makokou, Gabon, 3.1.1964, van Bree leg., Amsterdam 7507; L = 3164/4/3" [on the label "*Lukoschuskaaia makokoui* Kolebinova"].
- Walchiidae
- *Gahrlipeia (Giroudia) liberiensis* Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean – (Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean, 1978: 124 [6 slides]). Label data: "Paratype[s], larvae, ex *Lophuromys sikapusi* [Muridae], Njeble, Liberia, 16.10.1970, Voelker leg., Hamburg T 882; L = 181070/N/2; G/8; G/9; G/10; G/11; G/16".
 - *Gahrlipeia (Gateria) megaspis* Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean – (Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean, 1978: 122). Label data: "Paratype larva, ex *Lophuromys sikapusi* [Muridae], Njeble, Liberia, 16.10.1970, Voelker leg., Hamburg T 882; L = 161010/M/2".
 - *Schoutedenichia (Schoutedenichia) corsica* Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean – (Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean, 1971: 259 [3 slides]). 1. Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Crocidura russula* [Soricidae], Lama, Corse, France, 6.10.1967, P. Beron leg., 17/17". 2. Label data: "Paratype[s], ex *Crocidura russula* [Soricidae], Lama, Corse, France, 6.10.1967, P. Beron leg., 1/17; 2/17".
 - *Schoutedenichia (Schoutedenichia) frici* Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean – (Kolebinova & Vercammen-Grandjean, 1980: 67). Label data: "Paratype larva, ex *Crocidura?*, Kanarischeli, 12.11.1887, NHM Wien, Lukoschus leg.; L = 12111887/2".
 - *Schoutedenichia (Schoutedenichia) thracica* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1966: 675). Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Apodemus sylvaticus* [Muridae], Stara Zagora, Bulgaria, 24.7.1961, M. Kolebinova leg., 5/58 – 32".
 - *Neoschoengastia (Neoschoengastia) rustica* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1974b: 1113 [5 slides]). 1. Label data: "Holotype larva, ex *Apodemus sylvaticus* [Muridae], Kalugerovo, distr. Pazardzik, Bulgarie, 17.3.1970, V. Levi leg., 28/268". 2–3. Label data: "Paratype[s], larvae, ex *Apodemus sylvaticus*, Kalugerovo, distr. Pazardzik, Bulgarie, 17.3.1970, V. Levi leg., 1-4/268".

- *Sasatrombicula (Sasatrombicula) bureschi* Kolebinova & Beron – (Kolebinova & Beron, 1965: 71). Label data: “Holotype larva, ex *Rhinolophus hipposideros* [Rhinolophidae], Gramatikovo, Strandja, Bulgaria, 8.12.1963, P. Beron leg., 1/7”.
- *Sasatrombicula (R[udnicula]) balcanica* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1966: 74 [2 slides – holotype and ?]). Label data: “Holotype larva, ex *Rhinolophus ferrumequinum* [Rhinolophidae], Stranja, Bulgaria, 8.12.1963, P. Beron leg., 3/12”.
- *Sasatrombicula mediterranea* Kolebinova – (Kolebinova, 1966). Label data: “Paratype larva, ex *Rhinolophus hipposideros* [Rhinolophidae], Cave Crionerida, Crete, Greece, 15.01.1968, P. Beron leg., No 24/d”.

Leeuwenhoekiiidae

- *Straelensia europea* Vercammen-Grandjean & Kolebinova – (Vercammen-Grandjean & Kolebinova, 1968: 250). Label data: “Holotype larva, ex *Canis lupus* [Canidae], Primorsko, [Distr.] Burgas, 28.5.1965, M. Kolebinova leg., 7/224 – 163”.

Vatacaridae

- *Babiangia (Iguanacarus) danieli* Dusbábek & Černý – (Dusbábek & Černý, 1970). Currently *Vatacarus danieli* (Dusbábek & Černý, 1970). Label data: “Paratype, 1 larva, ex *Thalasseus sandwicensis* [Sternidae], El Socorro, Cuba, 13.3.1965, V. Černý, J. de la Cruz leg.”.

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